

INFLUENCE OF VALUES-BASED FAMILY ROUTINES, QUALITY OF TEACHER-STUDENT INTERACTION AND DISCIPLINE PRACTICES ON THE KINDERGARTNERS' SOCIO-EMOTIONAL SKILLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19533180>

ABSTRACT

Early childhood is a critical period of development that shapes children's behavior, relationships, and preparation for formal schooling. Despite the growing recognition of socio-emotional skills development in early childhood education, limited research has examined how family routines and classroom interactions collectively influence kindergartners' socio-emotional skills in faith-based educational settings. This descriptive-correlational study investigated the influence of values-based family routines, quality of teacher–student interaction, and discipline practices on the socio-emotional skills of kindergartners in a faith-based institution in Cagayan de Oro City during the School Year 2025–2026. Data were collected using modified, content-validated, and reliability-tested Likert-scale checklists administered to kindergartners and their parents. Descriptive statistics including the mean, frequency, percentage, and standard deviation, Canonical Correlation Analysis, and Multiple Regression Analysis, were used to analyze the data. Findings revealed that values-based family routines, quality of teacher–student interaction, and discipline practices were assessed to a high extent, as well. Meanwhile, kindergartners' socio-emotional skills were at a generally moderate level. Canonical correlation analysis showed that discipline practices were significantly associated with the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills. Regression results showed that collectively the independent variables such as values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, and discipline practices significantly influenced socio-emotional skills; however, only discipline practices emerged as a significant individual predictor. Further research can be developed based on the current study by researchers using broader and

more diverse sample sizes and child-friendly activities to have a better understanding of the classroom dynamics and interactions among peers.

Keywords: *values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, discipline practices, socio-emotional skills*

INTRODUCTION

The formative kindergarten years in an early childhood environment lay the holistic foundation for a child, mainly in shaping cognitive, psychomotor, affective, and socio-emotional skills. Rais and Haddar (2024) suggest that this foundation also influence their emotional bonds with other individuals, promote cooperation, empathy, self-control, and responsible decision-making, which enables them to adapt to the demands of various environments, such as school and society. These skills are essential in kindergartners as they lay the groundwork for academic success.

Abd (2024) espoused that promoting a positive and constructive discipline emphasizes a respectful viewpoint towards empathy and self-regulation in the children's environment, contradicting traditional disciplinary strategies such as verbal reprimand and corporal punishment. Additionally, Ndlovu (2021) noted that in today's contemporary generation, positive discipline is mainly understood and practiced by most parents in varied households but remains uncertain and inconsistent within socioeconomic and diverse cultural contexts. This reminds us of the crucial role that families, especially parents, play in shaping the emotional well-being and social development of children during the formative years.

Furthermore, the kindergarten children's context relies on social interaction and emotional regulation, which are, in fact, interrelated with values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, and discipline practices. Understanding these factors influencing kindergartners' socio-emotional skills can provide insights for educators, parents, kindergarten children, school administrators, and future researchers in promoting more diverse child development. This research study seeks to widen beyond varied perspectives in combining the influence of values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, and discipline practices on the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills, especially in kindergarten, to discuss varied evidence-based practices that help and support them in their holistic growth and development.

Moreover, this research study is in line with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The study is directly connected with SDG 4: Quality Education since it focuses on the fact that cognitive learning is not the only quality of education in early childhood; however, the socio-emotional skills growth of children also has to be considered. The research indicates that the skill to form self-regulation, empathy, and relationship skills by kindergartners is influenced by significant experiences at home and at school. Values-Based Family Routines that are guided by value-embedded traditions, emotional climate of routines, and communication patterns in routines, leading them to become better prepared to learn and engage in society. Quality

Teacher-Student Interaction leads to a positive, inviting, and interactive classroom atmosphere in which children feel mentored, supported, and encouraged to learn. Similarly, the discipline practices provide the child with explicit expectations, support, and positive feedback, which enhance their emotional and social development. The combination of these three factors in the work will form a solid ground towards holistic child development, which is one of the objectives of quality education. In this way, the paper contributes to SDG 4 as it demonstrates that kindergartners enjoy greater educational experiences when their socio-emotional skills development is supported by both family and school-based support systems.

Research Questions

The research study aimed to determine the influence of values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction and discipline practices on the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills. The study was conducted in a faith-based institution during the School Year 2025-2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do the kindergartners' assess the value-based family routines considering:
 - 1.1 Value-Embedded Traditions;
 - 1.2 Emotional Climate of Routines; and
 - 1.3 Communication Patterns in Routines?
2. What is the kindergartners' assessment of the quality of teacher-student interaction in terms of:
 - 2.1 Relational Warmth and Closeness;
 - 2.2 Children Engagement Support; and
 - 2.3 Behavior Support and Guidance?
3. What is the kindergartners' assessment of their discipline practices considering:
 - 3.1 Use of encouragement and praise;
 - 3.2 Use of clear expectations and boundaries;
 - 3.3 Use of natural and logical consequences; and
 - 3.4 Use of non-violent responses?
4. What is the kindergartners' level of socio-emotional skills as assessed by the kindergarten teacher in terms of:
 - 4.1 Self-regulation;
 - 4.2 Empathy; and
 - 4.3 Relationship skills?
5. Are the kindergartners' values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, and their parents' discipline practices significantly associated with their socio-emotional skills?
6. Do values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, and discipline practices significantly influence the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills?

METHODOLOGY

Research Participants and Sampling Procedure

The participants of the study consisted of kindergarten learners enrolled in a faith-based educational institution. The total population comprised 138 pupils distributed across seven (7) sections. To determine the appropriate sample size, the Taro Yamane formula for sample size determination was employed. Based on this computation, a sample of 105 kindergarten learners was obtained to serve as the participants of the study. The number of participants from each section was computed proportionately based on the size of each section relative to the total population. The sample size for each section was determined, and participants were selected using simple random sampling, which ensured that all pupils in a section had an equal chance of being selected, thereby reducing the likelihood of selection bias.

Research Instruments

The primary research instruments for this study were modified from various authors using five-point Likert-scale checklists to assess the value-based family routines, the quality of teacher-student interaction, parents' discipline practices and the questionnaire in assessing the socio-emotional skills of kindergartners. The checklist was designed in an age-appropriate way for kindergartners, with simple, concrete sentences, short sentences, and visual indicators, such as emoticons and emojis, based on the Emoji-Based Visual Analog Scale. Moisset et al. (2022) authors of the visual analog scale, highlight scales with faces were used because pictorial/emoticon/emoji based scales are effective scales that have long been used with children due to the fact that young children may not be able to reliably use numeric or verbal scales, therefore, the authors provided that emoji-based scales might be necessary in children that explains why emoticons and emojis checklist are suggested to be used with kindergartners aged participants.

The items on values-based family routines were from Shachnai and Daniel (2020). Modifications were made to fit the context of this study. Meanwhile, the items on the quality of teacher-student interaction were from Wang. et al. (2024).

Moreover, to assess parents' positive discipline practices, a comprehensive questionnaire adapted from the Positive Discipline Parenting Scale (PDPS) of Paul Carroll and Kyle Hamilton (2020) authors of the "Positive Discipline Parenting Scale Reliability and Validity of a Measure," examined how PDPS relates with other parenting styles. Lastly, to assess the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills (SES), the study utilized a standardized Socio-Emotional Skills Rating Scale espoused by Gresham et al. (2020) which consists of a five-point Likert scale, which were administered by the kindergarten teachers, focusing on three essential dimensions: self-regulation, empathy, and relationship skills.

Data Gathering Procedure and Ethical Considerations

This research study employed a face-to-face data gathering process. Preparation, administration, data collection, and interpretation comprised the procedures implemented. The researcher obtained the ethical clearance from the Research Ethics Committee of Lourdes College. When the approval was obtained, the researcher asked permission from the school principal. Then, informed consent and assent form were distributed to the participating kindergartners, kindergarten teachers and parents to ensure voluntary research participation.

The data gathered in the study were anonymized to protect the participants' privacy and ensure completeness. Individual data were not included in the data set, such as names, contacts, and school information. The participants were allocated their own codes, and the codes were utilized during the data encoding, data analysis, and data reporting. The list of codes to real identities were stored separately, and confidentially, only the researcher was allowed access to the list. The presentation of the results were in aggregate form such that no specific person can be identified.

Physical documents were kept in a locked cabinet, whereas electronic data will be stored in password-protected and encrypted storage devices. Physical documents shall be destroyed at the end of this time slot, and electronic data shall be permanently deleted.

As per the common ethical research practices and the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all the anonymized data will be stored within five (5) years of the study completion to verify and use the data in academic work. This study complies with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173), integrating with Belmont Principles. According to Miracle (2016) it consists of Respect for Persons, Beneficence, and Justice, emphasizing commitment to protecting the personal and sensitive information that participants provide. Respect for Persons emphasized voluntary research participation and was observed throughout the research study, as reflected in the informed consent and assent forms, ensuring that all research participants are aware of the entire research purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits. Beneficence was ensured by designing the research study correctly to utilize potential benefits and minimize any harm that may be incurred during its implementation, including securing personal data from abuse and exploitation. Justice was exercised, ensuring all participants were chosen fairly and had equal access to the benefits of the research study. Thus, the research study was entirely voluntary, and participants were free to withdraw at any moment without facing consequences. Data and information that are collected throughout this study are used solely for academic purposes and are handled with the strictest confidentiality.

All the participants were made aware of their freedom to pull out of the study any time without repercussions or punishment.

The researcher in this study was merely a researcher and played no role in serving as an intervention provider. The researcher was only involved in seeking the required permissions, administering validated and reliable research instruments, liaising with the school administrators and teachers, gathering data and performing statistical analysis and

interpretation. There was no instructional therapy, behavioral therapy or therapeutic intervention and no adjustment of routine everyday classroom practices and teaching methods in the process of conducting the study. Such definition of roles was meant to eliminate role conflict, reduce the researcher influence, and tackle ethical issues associated with authority considering that the participants were kindergartners'

Regardless of these handling, some limitations regarding the role of the researcher were identified, such as the risk of response bias, social desirability bias, and subjectivity in the data rated by teachers and collected by parents. Also, the use of self-report and rating scales restricted the degree to which behaviors would have been independently corroborated. These limitations were addressed by using standardized measures whose reliability has been ensured, provision of anonymity and confidentiality and the strict adherence to the ethical standards in the form of voluntary participation, informed consent, child assent, and data privacy provisions.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were used to interpret the data that were gathered:

For Research Questions 1, 2, 3, and 4, descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were employed to describe the discipline practices that parents are practicing, values-based family routines, and quality of teacher-student interaction of kindergartners, as well as the socio-emotional skills.

For Research Question 5, Canonical Correlation Analysis was used to determine whether participants' values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, and discipline practices were significantly related to the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills.

For Research Question 6, Multiple Regression Analysis was employed to find out if the participants' values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, and discipline practices significantly influenced the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

This research study focused on investigating influence of values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction and discipline practices on the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills. Values-based family routines were limited to the use of value-embedded traditions, emotional climate of routines, and communication patterns in routines. Subsequently, quality of teacher-student interaction emphasized relational warmth and closeness, children's engagement support, and behavior support and guidance. Meanwhile, discipline practices were limited to the use of encouragement and praise, use of clear expectations and boundaries, use of natural and logical consequences, and use of non-violent responses.

Socio-emotional skills encompassed the following: self-regulation, empathy, and relationship skills. Thus, this covered kindergarten children aged 5 years old who were currently enrolled in the kindergarten of a faith-based institution in Cagayan de Oro. The

participants, who include both the children of the parents and their kindergarten teachers, actively participated in this research study. The kindergartners, the primary source of information regarding values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, and parents are the secondary source for the positive discipline practices. At the same time, kindergarten teachers also assessed the socio-emotional skills of the children.

RESULTS

Research Question 1. How do the kindergartners assess the value-based family routines considering:

- 1.1 Value-Embedded Traditions;
- 1.2 Emotional Climate; and
- 1.3 Communication Patterns?

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of the Kindergartners' Assessment of their Value-Based Routines considering Value-Embedded Traditions

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	15	13.64
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	65	59.09
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	30	27.27
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	0	0.00
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			110	100
Overall Mean				3.88
SD				0.55
Interpretation				High

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I say "please" when I ask for something at home.	4.02	0.82	Often
2. I say "thank you" when someone helps me at home.	3.92	0.64	Often
3. I put away my toys after playing at home.	3.88	0.69	Often
4. I follow the rules set by my family at home.	3.84	0.63	Often
5. I help my family members when they need help at home.	3.76	0.63	Often

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of the Kindergartners' Assessment of their Value-Based Routines considering Emotional Climate

Indicators			Mean	SD	Description
1. I feel happy at home.			4.20	1.03	Often
2. I feel safe to share my feelings.			3.69	1.39	Often
3. My family is kind when I make mistakes.			3.63	1.34	Often
4. My family shows love to me.			4.26	1.03	Often
5. I feel cared for at home.			4.10	1.12	Often
Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage	
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	33	30.00	
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	47	42.73	
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	24	21.82	
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	6	5.45	
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0.00	
Total			110	100	
Overall Mean			3.98		
SD			0.83		
Interpretation			High		

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics of the Kindergartners' Assessment of their Value-Based Routines considering Communication Patterns

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage	
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	26	23.64	
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	29	26.36	
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	49	44.55	
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	3	2.73	
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	3	2.73	
Total			110	100	
Overall Mean			3.65		
SD			0.90		
Interpretation			High		

Indicators		Mean	SD	Description
1. I talk to my family every day.		3.83	1.12	Often
2. My family listens when I talk.		3.75	1.30	Often
3. My family explains house rules to me.		3.09	1.52	Sometimes
4. I can ask questions at home.		3.41	1.28	Sometimes

5. We talk together as a family. 4.16 1.09 Often

Table 4

Summary Table of the Kindergartners' Assessment of Value-Based Family Routines

Value-Based Family Routines	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Value-Embedded Traditions	3.88	0.55	High
Emotional Climate	3.98	0.83	High
Communication Patterns in Routines	3.65	0.90	High
Overall Mean	3.84	0.59	High

Legend:

Range	Description	Interpretation
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low

Research Question 2. What is the kindergartners' assessment of the quality of teacher-student interaction in terms of:

- 2.1. Relational Warmth and Closeness;
- 2.2. Children Engagement Support; and
- 2.3. Behavior Support and Guidance?

Table 5

Descriptive Statistics of the Kindergartners' Assessment of their Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction in terms of Relational Warmth and Closeness

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	75	68.18
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	27	24.55
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	8	7.27
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	0	0.00
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			110	100
Overall Mean			4.55	
SD			0.56	
Interpretation			Very High	

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. My teacher smiles and speaks kindly to me.	4.39	0.77	Often
2. My teacher comforts me when I am upset.	4.67	0.65	Always
3. I feel safe to talk to my teacher.	4.55	0.71	Always
4. My teacher shows patience with me.	4.41	0.85	Often
5. My teacher treats me with care and respect.	4.73	0.59	Always

Table 6

Descriptive Statistics of the Kindergartners' Assessment of their Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction in terms of Children Engagement Support

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	83	75.45
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	22	20.00
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	2	1.82
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	3	2.73
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			110	100
Overall Mean			4.63	
SD			0.64	
Interpretation			Very High	

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. My teacher listens when I speak.	4.59	0.79	Always
2. My teacher responds to my questions carefully.	4.63	0.70	Always
3. My teacher explains things in a way I understand more.	4.65	0.61	Always
4. My teacher encourages me to share ideas.	4.55	0.92	Always
5. My teacher gives me time to talk to my classmates.	4.73	0.75	Always

Table 7

Descriptive Statistics of the Kindergartners' Assessment of the Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction in terms of Behavior Support and Guidance

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	83	75.45
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	22	20.00
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	2	1.82
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	3	2.73
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			110	100

	Overall Mean	SD	4.67
	SD	0.62	Very High
	Interpretation		
Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. My teacher reminds me of the classroom rules.	4.75	0.68	Always
2. My teacher praises me good behavior.	4.57	0.72	Always
3. My teacher helps me to solve problems easily.	4.72	0.64	Always
4. My teacher guides when I make mistakes.	4.64	0.82	Always
5. My teacher encourages me to try again.	4.67	0.78	Always

Table 8

Summary Table of Kindergartners' Assessment on the Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction

Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Relational Warmth and Closeness	4.55	0.56	Very High
Children Engagement Support	4.63	0.64	Very High
Behavior Support and Guidance	4.67	0.62	Very High
Overall	4.62	0.57	Very High

Legend:

Range	Description	Interpretation
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low

Research Question 3. What is the parents' assessment of their discipline practices considering:

- 3.1 use of encouragement and praise;
- 3.2 use of clear expectations and boundaries;
- 3.3 use of natural and logical consequences; and
- 3.4 use of non-violent responses?

Table 9

Descriptive Statistics of the Parents' Assessment of their Discipline Practices in terms of Use of Encouragement and Praise

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	16	14.55
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	90	81.82
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	4	3.63
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	0	0
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0
Total			110	100
Overall Mean				4.11
SD				0.36
Interpretation				High

Use of Encouragement and Praise	Mean	SD	Description
1. I praise my child for trying, even when the task is difficult.	3.72	0.68	Often
2. I encourage my child to try new activities or tasks.	4.82	0.39	Always
3. I give verbal praise when my child shows good behavior.	3.78	0.70	Often
4. I give positive feedback when my child follows simple rules.	4.41	0.56	Often
5. I acknowledge my child's small achievements or improvements.	3.80	0.65	Often

Table 10

Descriptive Statistics of the Parents' Assessment of their Discipline Practices in terms of Use of Clear Expectations and Boundaries

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	24	21.82
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	82	74.55
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	4	3.63
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	0	0
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0
Total			110	100
Overall Mean				4.14
SD				0.39
Interpretation				High

Use of Clear Expectations and Boundaries	Mean	SD	Description
1. I clearly explain the rules and expectations at home.	4.02	0.82	Often
2. I remind my child of household limits in a calm and respectful way.	3.92	0.64	Often
3. I explain the reasons behind the rules to my child.	4.51	0.50	Always
4. I am consistent in enforcing household rules.	4.51	0.50	Always
5. I discuss household rules with my child and listen to their opinions.	3.76	0.63	Often

Table 11

Descriptive Statistics of the Parents' Assessment of their Discipline Practices in terms of Use of Natural and Logical Consequences

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	42	38.18
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	54	49.09
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	14	12.73
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	0	0
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0
Total			110	100
Overall Mean				4.21
SD				0.55
Interpretation				High

Use of Natural and Logical Consequences	Mean	SD	Description
1. I allow my child to learn from the consequences of their actions.	4.20	1.03	Often
2. I help my child understand how their actions affect others.	4.68	0.47	Always
3. I use logical consequences when correcting my child.	3.82	0.74	Often
4. I explain to my child why a consequence is given.	4.26	1.03	Often
5. I allow my child to correct their mistakes and learn from them.	4.10	1.12	Often

Table 12

Descriptive Statistics of the Parents' Assessment of their Discipline Practices in terms of Use of Non-Violent and Respectful Responses

Use of Non-Violent and Respectful Responses	Mean	SD	Description
1. I manage my child's misbehavior without shouting.	4.39	0.77	Often
2. I manage my emotion when correcting my child's mistakes.	4.51	0.50	Always
3. I talk to my child about their feelings before disciplining.	4.55	0.71	Always
4. I use gentle communication when my child misbehaves.	4.73	0.45	Always
5. I show respect for my child's emotions during discipline moments.	4.73	0.59	Always

Table 13

Summary Table of Parents' Assessment of their Discipline Practices

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	68	61.82
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	40	36.36
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	2	1.82
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	0	0
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0
Total			110	100
Overall Mean				4.58
SD				0.35
Interpretation				Very High

Discipline Practices	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Encouragement and Praise	4.11	0.36	High
Clear Expectations and Boundaries	4.14	0.39	High
Natural and Logical Consequences	4.21	0.55	High
Non-Violent Responses	4.58	0.35	Very High
Overall Mean	4.26	0.25	High

Legend:

Range	Description	Interpretation
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low

Research Question 4. What is the kindergartners' level of socio-emotional skills as assessed by the kindergarten teacher in terms of:

- 4.1 Self-Regulation;
- 4.2 Empathy; and
- 4.3 Relationship skills?

Table 14

Descriptive Statistics of the Teachers' Assessment on the Kindergartners' Socio-Emotional Skills in terms of Self-Regulation

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	0	0.00
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	64	58.18
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	46	41.82
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	0	0.00
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			110	100
Mean				3.56
SD				0.35
Interpretation				High

A. Self-Regulation	Mean	SD	Description
<i>The child . . .</i>			
1. demonstrates self-management by staying focused without reminders.	3.76	0.75	Often
2. having difficulty controlling my impulses and following directions.	3.70	0.71	Often
3. can calm down independently after being upset.	3.45	0.69	Sometimes
4. gets impatient and struggle to wait for my turn during activities.	3.48	0.81	Sometimes
5. maintains attention during class routines or tasks.	3.42	0.78	Sometimes

Table 15

Descriptive Statistics of the Teachers' Assessment on the Kindergartners' Socio-Emotional Skills in terms of Empathy

Score Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	6	5.45
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	64	58.18
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	40	36.36
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	0	0.00
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			110	100
Mean				3.77
SD				0.50
Interpretation				High

Empathy	Mean	SD	Description
<i>The child . . .</i>			
1. notices others' feelings and often responds with kindness and concern.	3.72	0.68	Often
2. does not offer help or comfort when a classmate is upset.	3.71	0.76	Often
3. shows understanding when others make mistakes.	3.78	0.70	Often
4. ignores when someone is hurt or sad.	3.85	0.64	Often
5. uses polite and caring words when talking to peers.	3.80	0.65	Often

Table 16

Descriptive Statistics of the Teachers' Assessment on the Kindergartners' Socio-Emotional Skills in terms of Relationship Skills

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High	0	0.00
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High	24	21.82
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate	78	70.91
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low	8	7.27
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			110	100
Mean				3.08
SD				0.48
Interpretation				Moderate

Relationship Skills <i>The child . . .</i>	Mean	SD	Description
1. forms and maintains friendships with peers.	3.11	0.91	Sometimes
2. does not cooperate well during team or pair activities.	3.45	0.79	Sometimes
3. resolves peer conflicts peacefully with the help of adults (parents and kindergarten teachers) guidance.	2.73	0.84	Sometimes
4. having difficulty communicating effectively with peers and kindergarten teachers.	3.39	0.88	Sometimes
5. shows willingness to apologize or make amends when necessary.	2.72	0.87	Sometimes

Table 17

Summary Table of the Teachers' Assessment of the Kindergartners' Socio-Emotional Skills

Socio-Emotional Skills	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Self-Regulation	3.56	0.35	High
Empathy	3.77	0.50	High
Relationship Skills	3.08	0.48	Moderate
Overall	3.47	0.29	Moderate

Legend:

Range	Description	Interpretation
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low

Research Question 5. Are the kindergartners' values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, and their parents' discipline practices significantly associated with their socio-emotional skills?

H₀₁: The kindergartners' values-based family routines are not significantly associated with their socio-emotional skills.

H₀₂: The quality of teacher-student interaction is not significantly associated with the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills.

H₀₃: The kindergartners' parents' discipline practices are not significantly associated with their socio-emotional skills.

Table 18

Canonical Correlation Analysis Between Values-Based Family Routines and Socio-Emotional Skills

Variable	Cross loading	R _c	R _c ²	F(9, 253)	p
Values-Based Family Routines					
Value Embedded Traditions	0.64				
Emotional Climate of Routines	0.17				
Communication Patterns in Routines	0.10	0.65	0.42	7.178*	<.001
Socio-Emotional Skills					
Self-Regulation	-0.06				
Empathy	0.65				
Relationship Skills	-0.01				

*Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level.

Table 19

Canonical Correlation Analysis Between Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction and Socio-Emotional Skills

Variable	Cross loading	R _c	R _c ²	F(9, 253)	p
Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction					
Relational Warmth and Closeness	0.21				
Children Engagement Support	0.05				
Behavior Support and Guidance	0.12	0.29	0.08	1.189	0.302
Socio-Emotional Skills					
Self-Regulation	-0.04				
Empathy	0.28				
Relationship Skills	0.08				

*Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level.

Table 20

Canonical Correlation Analysis Between Discipline Practices and Socio-Emotional Skills

Variable	Cross loading	R _c	R _c ²	F(12, 273)	p
Discipline Practices					
Encouragement and Praise	0.87	0.88	0.77	17.012*	<.001

Clear Expectations and Boundaries	0.54
Natural and Logical Consequences	0.03
Non-Violent Responses	0.31
Socio-Emotional Skills	
Self-Regulation	-0.01
Empathy	0.87
Relationship Skills	0.08

*Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level.

Research Question 6. Do the kindergartners' values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction and discipline practices significantly influence their socio-emotional skills?

H₀4: The kindergartners' values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction and discipline practices do not significantly influence their socio-emotional skills.

H₀5: The kindergartners' values-based family routines do not significantly influence their socio-emotional skills.

H₀6: The quality of teacher-student interaction does not significantly influence their socio-emotional skills.

H₀7: The parents' discipline practices do not significantly influence their socio-emotional skills.

Table 21

Regression Analysis of Values-Based Family Routines, Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction, and Discipline Practices on Socio-Emotional Skills

Predictor	Unstandardized Coefficients		β	95% CI		t	p
	B	SE		Lower	Upper		
Constant	2.34	0.36		1.638	3.050	6.580*	<.001
Values-Based Family Routines	-0.09	0.08	-0.184	-0.238	0.060	-1.18	0.240
Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction	-0.07	0.06	-0.139	-0.187	0.049	-1.17	0.246
Discipline Practices	0.58*	0.19	0.511	0.213	0.954	3.12	0.002

Model Summary

R = 0.322 R² = 0.104 Adjusted R² = 0.079 F(3,106) = 4.10* p=0.009

Note. *B* = unstandardized beta coefficient, *SE* = standard error, β = standardized beta coefficient, 95% *CI* = 95% confidence interval, *t* = *t* statistic, *p* = probability value.
*Significant at 0.01 two-tailed alpha level.

Model Equation: $S = 0.58D + 2.34$

Legend: *S* = Socio-Emotional Skills, *D* = Discipline Practices

DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. How do the kindergartners assess the value-based family routines considering:

- 1.1 Value-Embedded Traditions;
- 1.2 Emotional Climate; and
- 1.3 Communication Patterns?

Table 1

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the kindergartners' assessment of their value-based family routines based in terms of value-embedded traditions. It can be gleaned that they have assessed their value-embedded traditions as generally high, as indicated by the overall mean of 3.88, with a standard deviation of 0.55. Cueli (2024) emphasized that these value-based family routines are also associated with increased prosocial behavior, emotional regulation, and adaptive functioning among children, because children acquire values through observed behavior and participatory interaction in the family. This implies that participants tend to have strong value-based family routines, such as significant values like respect, responsibility, love, and cooperation, which are not just taught orally but also demonstrated in the day-to-day activities of a family.

Table 2

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics data of the kindergartners' assessment of their value-based routines regarding the emotional climate of routines. The overall mean of 3.98 and the standard deviation of 0.83 may be considered high. This demonstrates that the family's routine communication is generally high-level. Wang. et al. (2024) advocated that compared to those grown in disorganized, unresponsive, or hostile family conditions, those in emotionally supportive and cohesive family environments demonstrated better emotional and social functioning that led to the emergence of emotional regulation skills of children, social adaptation, and social belonging. This would mean that a high emotional climate also means that children most probably experience family environments where they feel loved, safe, heard and supported in their daily experiences.

Table 3

The descriptive statistics data of communication patterns in routines are presented in Table 3. The table shows that the kindergartners assessed their communication patterns as high, as revealed in an overall mean of 3.65, interpreted as high. This indicates that most children can express themselves, listen to others, and interact appropriately in their daily activities. It implies that they are able to contribute productively during class discussions, listen attentively when other people are talking, and also respond to them respectfully and with understanding. This observation aligns with the idea of Cabrera and Volling (2021) who described that effective and regular communication between parents and children in everyday routines can help children develop greater emotional knowledge, expressiveness, and secure attachment. Bierman et al. (2023) espoused that socio-emotional competence is built on the principle of supportive communication as its relational basis. This suggests that their home and school environments provide supportive opportunities for developing basic communication skills, which are essential for social interaction, emotional expression, and early learning.

Table 4

The summary of the findings of value-based family routines, value-embedded traditions, emotional climate routines, and communication patterns in routines is provided in Table 4. The table presents the mean scores, the standard deviations, and the interpretations for each dimension and the overall result. The overall mean of 3.84, interpreted as High, indicates that kindergartners generally experience a family environment rich in value-based routines. The results align with the study by Prime et al. (2020), who underscored that predictable, value-based routines in families serve as developmental settings in which children learn to regulate their emotions, adhere to social norms, and feel a sense of belonging. These routines offer organization and purpose in children's daily lives, thereby sustaining their socio-emotional development.

Research Question 2. What is the kindergartners' assessment of the quality of teacher-student interaction in terms of:

- 2.1. Relational Warmth and Closeness;
- 2.2. Children Engagement Support; and
- 2.3. Behavior Support and Guidance?

Table 5

Table 5 presents kindergartners' assessment of the quality of teacher-student interaction in terms of relational warmth and closeness with the teacher. The overall mean of 4.55, interpreted as high, means that kindergartners generally perceive their interactions with teachers as positive, warm, and supportive. This implies that teachers often exhibit nurturing practices, including caring, encouraging, and responding to

children's needs. As Allen (2021) implies that strong teacher–student relationships are present, fostering a sense of trust and belonging that can enhance students' motivation, engagement, and overall learning experience. This degree of positive relationships suggests that children are delighted, appreciated, and safe in the classroom atmosphere, which is crucial to their emotional well-being.

Table 6

Table 6 presents the participants' perceptions of Children's Engagement Support. The results show that most participants rated the teacher's support for engagement as very high, as indicated in an overall mean of (4.63) and a standard deviation of (0.64), which is indicative of students' perception of their teacher as very supportive of their classroom activities. This result finds consonance with what Xu et al. (2023) indicated that the teacher creates a positive learning atmosphere that encourages participation in classroom activities, awakening, and purposeful involvement in the daily activities of the classroom. This finding implies that while teachers effectively facilitate communication, further encouraging idea-sharing may enhance students' confidence, self-expression, and active participation in classroom learning.

Table 7

Data on Behavior Support and Guidance, based on participants' perceptions, are presented in Table 7. The overall mean of 4.67 with a standard deviation of 0.62 falls within the Very High range, indicating that students perceive their teacher as consistently offering relevant behavioral instruction and support. This further means that teachers regularly remind the kindergarten pupils of rules, guide them when mistakes occur, encourage them to try again, and use supportive strategies rather than punitive ones. Moreover, this suggests that the classroom environment is well-structured, nurturing, and focused on helping the kindergartners learn appropriate behavior through understanding and encouragement.

Table 8

Table 8 shows the summary outcomes of the various dimensions of teacher–student interaction, such as: Relational Warmth and Closeness, Children's Engagement Support, and Behavior Support and Guidance. The overall mean of 4.62, interpreted as Very High, indicates that students perceive the quality of teacher–student interaction as consistently positive and supportive across all dimensions. The implication of such a finding is that such a teacher creates a healthy learning atmosphere that encourages active participation, attention, and valuable engagement in the activities that occur in the classroom on a day-to-day basis.

Research Question 3. What is the parents' assessment of their discipline practices considering:

- 3.1 use of encouragement and praise;
- 3.2 use of clear expectations and boundaries;

- 3.3 use of natural and logical consequences; and
- 3.4 use of non-violent responses?

Table 9

Table 9 presents the distribution of participants' assessment of the parents' discipline regarding the use of encouragement and praise. The data show that the parents assess their use of encouragement and praise as high, with an overall mean of 4.11. This implies that parents always encourage and praise their children, which makes children feel valued, inspired, and reassured about their potential. According to Robertson and Pay (2021) they stated that positive parental response, including the use of encouragement and praise, is associated with a sense of competence and motivation among children because they strengthen their efforts and develops confidence in themselves. It can also strengthen the parent-child relationship, making it more supportive and emotionally nurturing.

Table 10

Table 10 shows the distribution of parents' assessment of their discipline practices regarding the use of clear expectations and boundaries. The data show that parent-participants rated the use of clear expectations and boundaries as high, with an overall mean of 4.14. This means that parents consistently set and communicate rules, limits, and standards of behavior that their children can easily understand and follow.

Table 11

Table 11 shows the parent-participants' assessment of their discipline practices in terms of use of natural and logical consequences. The data show that parents highly use natural and logical consequences as revealed in an overall mean of 4.21. This implies that parents frequently allow their children to experience the direct and reasonable outcomes of their actions and use these moments as teaching opportunities rather than relying on punishment.

Table 12

Table 12 shows the parent-participants' assessment of their discipline practices in terms of the use of non-violent and respectful responses. It can be gleaned that they have very high use of non-violent and respectful responses, as revealed in the overall mean of 4.58. This indicates that they consistently manage their children's behavior through calm communication, patience, and understanding rather than through physical punishment or harsh verbal discipline. Recent literature by Quail and Ward (2023) supports this interpretation by showing that non-violent and respectful responses help parents maintain a safe and conducive environment for children and are relevant to attunement and secure attachment. Jeong et al. (2021) espoused that parents prioritize maintaining a positive and supportive parent-child relationship while modeling appropriate emotional regulation and respectful interaction.

Table 13

Table 13 shows the summary table of the parents' assessment of their discipline practices across four domains: use of encouragement and praise; clear expectations and boundaries; natural and logical consequences; and non-violent responses. It can be gleaned from the figures that as a whole, the parents assessed their discipline practices high as revealed in an overall mean of 4.26. This implies that parents perceive themselves as consistently using positive, effective, and appropriate discipline strategies in guiding their children's behavior. This suggests that they believe they are providing clear rules, encouragement, respectful communication, and constructive consequences rather than relying on harsh or punitive methods.

Research Question 4. What is the kindergartners' level of socio-emotional skills as assessed by the kindergarten teacher in terms of:

- 4.1 Self-Regulation;
- 4.2 Empathy; and
- 4.3 Relationship skills?

Table 14

Table 14 shows the descriptive statistics of the teachers' assessment of the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills in terms of self-regulation. The table shows that the kindergartners have high self-regulation as indicated by an overall mean of 3.56, which implies that they are generally able to manage their emotions, control their impulses, and follow rules or instructions appropriate to their age. In addition, these kindergartners can wait their turn, stay focused on tasks, handle frustration more calmly, and adjust their behavior in social and classroom situations.

Table 15

Table 15 indicates the descriptive statistics of the teachers' assessment of the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills in terms of empathy. The figures reveal that the kindergartners have high empathy skills, which means that they are able to recognize, understand, and respond appropriately to the feelings of others. This implies that they can show concern for peers who are upset, share or help when someone is in need, and adjust their behavior to be kind and supportive. This is supported by the majority of them (58.18%) who were rated as having high empathy skills.

Table 16

Table 16 shows an overall mean of 3.08, which implies that kindergarteners are able to interact, communicate, and cooperate with peers and adults. This implies that the children can be involved in simple social relations and can engage in group or partner relations in an acceptable way. The finding also indicates that relationship skills exist among the kindergarteners, and their future development can still be improved to ensure

that they can establish a stronger social competence and more stable positive interaction with others.

Table 17

Table 17 displays the summary table of the teachers' assessment of the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills. Overall, the figure reveals that the kindergartners have moderate socio-emotional skills as shown in an overall mean of 3.47. This result is consistent with the interpretation of Schoneveld and Brummelman (2023) who described that socio-emotional capability, including self-regulation or empathy, should be built up over time in a regular combination with parents, caring people, and teachers in early childhood. The interaction is beneficial as it enables children to acquire proper emotional expression, social knowledge, and prosocial behavior.

Research Question 5. Are the kindergartners' values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, and their parents' discipline practices significantly associated with their socio-emotional skills?

H₀₁: The kindergartners' values-based family routines are not significantly associated with their socio-emotional skills.

H₀₂: The quality of teacher-student interaction is not significantly associated with the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills.

H₀₃: The kindergartners' parents' discipline practices are not significantly associated with their socio-emotional skills.

Table 18

Table 18 shows the canonical correlation analysis between Values-Based Family Routines and Socio-Emotional Skills. The result reveals that there is a significant positive moderate canonical correlation between Values-Based Family Routines and Socio-Emotional Skills, $F(9, 253) = 7.178$, $p < .001$, $R_c = 0.65$, $R_c^2 = 0.42$. Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a meaningful, moderate-strength relationship between the way families consistently practice values-based routines and the socio-emotional skills of kindergartners (like self-regulation, empathy, and relationship skills).

Table 19

Table 19 shows the canonical correlation analysis between Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction and Socio-Emotional Skills. The result revealed that there is no significant canonical correlation between Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction and Socio-Emotional Skills, $F(9, 253) = 1.189$, $p = 0.302$, $R_c = 0.29$, $R_c^2 = 0.08$. Hence, the second null hypothesis cannot be rejected. The no significant canonical correlation between Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction and Socio-Emotional Skills implies that,

in this study, the way teachers interact with kindergartners through warmth, support, or instructional guidance did not show a meaningful influence on the children's socio-emotional development. This suggests that, for these students, factors outside the classroom, such as family routines, parenting practices, or home environment, may play a stronger role in shaping self-regulation, empathy, and relationship skills.

Table 20

Table 20 shows the canonical correlation analysis between Discipline Practices and Socio-Emotional Skills. The result revealed that there is a significant positive strong canonical correlation between Discipline Practices and Socio-Emotional Skills, $F(12, 273) = 17.012$, $p < .001$, $R_c = 0.88$, $R_c^2 = 0.77$. Therefore, the third null hypothesis is rejected. The finding underscores that how teachers manage behavior has something to do on how students develop emotionally and socially. Effective discipline practices are not just about maintaining order—they are foundational to nurturing well-rounded, emotionally competent learners.

Research Question 6. Do the kindergartners' values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction and discipline practices significantly influence their socio-emotional skills?

H₀₄: The kindergartners' values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction and discipline practices do not significantly influence their socio-emotional skills.

H₀₅: The kindergartners' values-based family routines do not significantly influence their socio-emotional skills.

H₀₆: The quality of teacher-student interaction does not significantly influence their socio-emotional skills.

H₀₇: The parents' discipline practices do not significantly influence their socio-emotional skills.

Table 21

Table 21 shows the multiple regression analysis predicting Socio-Emotional Skills from Values-Based Family Routines, Quality of Teacher-Student Interaction, and Discipline Practices. The model was statistically significant, $F(3, 106) = 4.10$, $p = 0.009$, $R = 0.322$, $R^2 = 0.104$. The finding indicates that 10.4% of the variation in the kindergartners' socio-emotional skills can be explained by the combined influence of values-based family routines, quality of teacher-student interaction, and discipline practices. Since the model was found to be statistically significant, the null hypothesis stating that these variables do not significantly influence socio-emotional skills, can be rejected (H_{04}). The finding underscores that socio-emotional skills are best developed through a synergistic approach—where families instill values, teachers build supportive

relationships, and discipline practices reinforce appropriate behavior. Together, these create an environment that nurtures emotionally intelligent and socially competent learners.

Conclusions

The research study concludes that the kindergartners typically go through values-based routines at home where they get to find emotional security, meaningful communication, and value development through daily family routines. Quality of teacher-student interaction in the classroom is understood to be highly supportive of relational warmth and closeness, learner engagement support, behavior support and guidance. Another strategy of discipline practices that is mostly used by parents focuses on respectful and non-violent responses, the use of clear expectations that are used to ensure that the children have a supportive environment in which they can grow. On the one hand, children demonstrate emerging socio-emotional skills, especially in empathy and self-management; on the other hand, relationship skills still have to be strengthened, in particular, by cooperating with peers and managing conflicts. Altogether, the findings suggest that family routines based on values and parental discipline are important variables that can be related to the socio-emotional skills of kindergartners, and the role of home environment in influencing the social and emotional performance of children can hardly be underestimated. Conversely, the quality of teacher-student interaction is rated very positively but fails to be a statistically significant predictor of the socio-emotional skills in this study, implying that the socio-emotional outcome in this case is more likely to be related to home-related factors.

The results of this study can be understood through the lens of Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory as they show that kindergartners' socio-emotional skills are influenced by factors within their microsystem, including family routines and teacher interactions. The significant role of discipline practices emphasizes the impact of proximal processes in the school environment, while the combined, albeit smaller, effects of family routines and teacher interaction highlight the interconnectedness of home and school environments in shaping socio-emotional development.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are presented:

- 1. Parents and Families** may enhance values-based family routines (e.g., regular family discussions, consistent traditions, and emotionally supportive family practices) in order to constantly foster socio-emotional development. Always uphold positive discipline through clarifying expectations and employing non-violent and respectful responses towards misbehavior. Enhance continuous encouragement and acknowledgement of praise through efforts to encourage confidence, empathy, and emotional management among children.

2. **Kindergarten Teachers** may train and provide support to kindergarten teachers with training and materials on structured SEL activities, particularly those focused on peer interaction and relationship-building. Supply parent training on positive discipline, emotional coaching, and positive family routines that aid in socio-emotional development at home.
3. **School Administrators** may offer planned classroom facilitations that develop relationship skills, including mediated cooperative play, facilitated solving of peer problems, role-playing of conflict management, and apologizing and making amends routines. Enhance home-school activities by aligning the classroom socio-emotional learning objectives with the parents by use of simple activities to be done at home that reinforce empathy, self-management, and peer relationship skills.
4. **Future Researchers** may conduct a replication of the study with wider or more varied samples and contexts to confirm the patterns present, especially the contribution of teacher-student interaction in the prediction of socio-emotional skills. Combine mixed methods (e.g., observations, interviews, child-friendly tasks) in order to observe the classroom dynamics and interactions with peers, which can be underrepresented in survey ratings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher confirms that this thesis adhered to the recommended ethical principles in conducting research involving human participants. All participants were informed in advance and provided their consent before taking part in the study, and this is because the purpose, procedures, and nature of the study were well explained to them.

Involvement in the study was voluntary, and the participants were allowed to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. The participants were guaranteed the anonymity and confidentiality of the information, and all the data gathered was processed as per the relevant data privacy laws. The participants were also considered in the research process, as their well-being was not subjected to any harm or discomfort. The researcher attests that they did not have a conflict of interest in the operations of this study. Moreover, plagiarism was also prevented, and references were recognized. Analysis of the results was done in an objective manner devoid of any kind of bias. The findings of the research were not used in any other way than academic and research purposes. Where the artificial intelligence tools were still used, full disclosure has been made to allow transparency and support the integrity of the research.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would wish to find this opportunity to sincerely thank all the individuals who provided their support, guidance, and encouragement in ensuring that this thesis is completed. To begin with, it is wise to express deep gratitude to the Almighty God who has been granting unending blessings, wisdom, strength, and guidance throughout the whole journey.

The researcher would also want to share the deepest sense of appreciation to his thesis adviser, Dr. Revina O. Mendoza, who made numerous suggestions, provided professional guidance, patience, and encouragement that were very instrumental in the completion of this thesis. Her patience, insights, and faith in the researcher have encouraged him not to give up even when there has been doubt. The researcher is endlessly grateful for her mentorship and kindness that went beyond the bounds of academic responsibility.

The researcher would like to express sincere gratitude to the esteemed panel members, Dr. Judith C. Chavez, Dr. Kriscentti Exzur P. Barcelona, Dr. Miguela B. Napiere, and Dr. Maria Alona A. Galendez, for their valuable insights, constructive comments, and thoughtful suggestions which greatly improved the quality of this study. Their time, expertise, and encouragement are deeply appreciated.

The school administrators, kindergarten teachers, parents, and kindergarteners are presented with special gratitude since, without their cooperation, trust, and willingness to give their time and answers, such a research study would not be possible.

The researcher also owes much love, understanding, moral support, and prayers from the family and friends during the execution of this research. Their support made them inspirational in fighting the hurdles along the way. The researcher appreciates saying that he is immensely thankful and loves his parents with unconditional love, sacrifices, prayers, understanding, and continuous support.

They all inspired and supported him, and that is what kept him inspired during the writing of this thesis manuscript. The researcher wishes to extend the thanks of everyone who, in some capacity, contributed to the success of this study. May God have a great blessing on you all.

The paper is aimed at all those who believe in the power of teaching and at the heart of every educator who is trying to change the lives of young learners.

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